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Generative AI and Children's Futures: New Research Challenges

By Tama Leaver, Curtin University, t.leaver@curtin.edu.au, and Suzanne Srdarov.

From *WALL·E* (Stanton, 2008) to *The Wild Robot* (Sanders, 2024), children's popular culture is filled with sympathetic, lovable, heroic artificial intelligence (AI) and robotic characters who make passionate and ethical choices about their own existence and help others. The AIs of contemporary cinema and television are often excellent role models. Indeed, popular culture has been one of the main ways that AI have entered mainstream imaginaries for more than half a century (Leaver, 2012). Yet even in popular culture, AI tend to be normative and in most cases coded white (Cave & Dihal, 2020). In feature films the creators of AI are similarly white male scientists the vast majority of the time (Cave et al., 2023). With the public launch of ChatGPT and other Generative AI (GenAI) tools in late 2022, for many people, young and old, AI emerged from popular culture into everyday life with surprising speed. Yet the GenAI tools that have emerged bear little resemblance to the AIs of popular culture. Instead, they emerge from the same contexts and cultures which have characterised big tech for two decades, driven by commercial imperatives and extractive logics (Crawford, 2021). With GenAI being integrated into a vast array of tools and platforms—from videogames and creative software to educational platforms and almost all social media—the rapid appearance and increasing impact of AI on children and young people demands urgent attention from researchers across a broad range of fields.

Researching Children and AI

In some respects, the rollout of GenAI simply supercharges existing challenges that have arisen from the way that the broader big tech companies operate, including their **disregard for personal privacy and thirst for young people's data**. GenAI tools run Large Language Models (LLMs) which, put simply, learn to statistically mimic certain types of outputs by absorbing as much content as can be found. More powerful models to date have been the ones that have absorbed even vaster amounts of data, drawing from every possible source, including scraping much of the content on the internet. In this context, the business of AI is the business of collecting as much data as possible, and this frequently includes the data of anyone using these tools, or anyone who has anything accessible online (Jones, 2024). Existing conventions where social media platforms are not supposed to collect the data of children under 13 (Reyes et al., 2018) have not been applied in the same ways to GenAI companies thus far, especially since data scraped from online sources is harvested indiscriminately.

Pangrazio and Selwyn (2023) warn that every new technological tool comes with a magical aura that positions it as too complex for everyday users to understand. However, they argue that like most technologies, AI is actually a very impressive combination of algorithms and mathematics which can be explained in an accessible

way. They highlight the ongoing importance of critical digital and data literacies: “everyone needs to be invested in maintaining and developing understandings of digital technologies and how they are generating, collecting, and using our data” (Pangrazio & Selwyn, 2023, p. 178). LLMs and other emerging AI are exciting in their new capabilities and affordances, but they are nevertheless still tools. To ensure children have opportunities to utilise these tools in creative, innovative, ethical and thoughtful ways, robust global commitment to ensuring a level of digital and critical data literacies is vital. This includes equipping young people with the skills to make informed choices about their own personal data and privacy.

Questions around copyright and the ownership are also provoked in terms of how training data is acquired for GenAI tools, and how the tools and their outputs will impact creative and related industries. The desire for more and more data to create larger and larger LLMs has seen AI companies acquire, scrape and extract content from a huge range of sources, but in most cases the content creators and copyright holders have not been consulted, informed or compensated. While this follows a similar logic to the US Fair Use which allows search engines to crawl the entire internet, with GenAI tools the justification is harder to argue since GenAI can create outputs which may be direct competitors with the copyrighted materials they were trained on (Baio, 2022). Ironically, artists and early adopters of GenAI tools are also dealing with the flipside of copyright law, with the outputs of LLMs mostly being considered uncopyrightable since they have been found to have “contained no human authorship” (Ropek, 2024). Yet for young people who aspire to any sort of creative career, will GenAI tools continue to on the one hand extract and exploit anything put online and, on the other hand, will these tools enhance or replace creative industries and future careers?

When tech companies do strike formal deals to use copyrighted material, new questions emerge. When major film studios are partnering with AI companies to train LLMs on entire film and television libraries (Lee, 2024), will this result in new opportunities for young people entering the creative industries in utilising these tools in creative and innovative ways, or will these partnerships provide film studios with short-term financial gains which lead to the automation of a raft of creative jobs in the future? Similarly, while any actual shifts in employment patterns may take some time, research is needed to shed light on how children and young people today imagine their future opportunities considering today’s AI hype.

Despite the hype and vast amount of capital driving the big AI companies, these **GenAI tools lack integrity** and frequently make any number of mistakes. Sometimes these mistakes are called hallucinations, but that language tends to reinforce the myth that GenAI have agentic human-like thoughts. It may well be clearer to say that GenAI tools glitch or, even more bluntly, produce multiple errors. GenAI tools can fabricate answers not because they lie, but because they have no understanding of the answers and content they create. Bender and colleagues have characterised LLMs as ‘stochastic parrots’, rightly emphasising that while GenAI might create convincing sounding outputs, GenAI actually have no idea whatsoever what they are creating or saying, rather this is the work of extremely sophisticated probabilistic models (Bender et al., 2021). Yet GenAI companies tend to double down, positioning these errors not as problematic, but as part of the pathway to even bigger and better AI. Indeed, under the guise of warning that superhuman AI is imminent, tech companies are mostly

exploiting these fears to tout the supposed supremacy of their own AI offerings, and drum up further business (Leaver & Srdarov, 2023).

However, as **more and more interactive agents utilising GenAI are released**—from chatbots to tools baked into a range of different software and apps—errors, glitches, hallucinations or any unexpected outputs can have very real consequences, especially for users who imagine these tools to be reliable. For young people engaging with GenAI-based tools via voice interfaces on smart speakers or smartphones, or in educational contexts, how they imagine these agents will very much frame their use. Since producing convincing real-time human-like conversation is now achievable with the latest GenAI tools, in many ways interacting with software agents backed with LLMs can produce interactions that may be difficult to distinguish from talking to an actual person. Building on existing analyses that explores the way people interact with digital assistants in smartphones and speakers (Kennedy & Strengers, 2022; Strengers & Kennedy, 2020), and the ways children interact with the ‘internet of toys’ (Holloway & Green, 2016; Mascheroni & Holloway, 2019), research is needed to understand the way children and young people interact with, and relate to, GenAI agents. This is especially urgent as these agents are rapidly appearing in the material and digital spaces that young people visit, and the tools they access and use as part of their everyday lives.

Given the indiscriminate extracting of data to train LLMs from a range of sources, including the internet, it is not surprising that these enormous data corpuses often contain **many types of bias**. These biases become increasingly problematic when GenAI amplifies this data in its probabilistic outputs, and when users of GenAI tools situate these outputs as fact. The potential of digital algorithms to reproduce harmful and oppressive racial biases is well established (Noble, 2018). This has the potential to be further amplified by GenAI as it dials these biases up from their origins into their most distilled forms. In an Australian context, for example, inclusion of Indigenous content poses issues around not only data sovereignty, but in representing Indigenous Australians in ways which are balanced, fair, inclusive and not “tokenistic” (Worrell, 2024). Users of AI turn to its tools to fill gaps in their knowledge, often having no framework for decoding the veracity of the output. Communicating the fallibility and biases of GenAI to users, and teaching them to read around and fact check, is vital to avoid compounding social issues that may be reproduced and exacerbated by AI. These literacies will need to be integrated from the earliest years of education if children are going to be able to critically contextualise GenAI outputs. There is thus a pressing need for research around the most effective strategies to expand digital literacy education to include AI literacies for young people as both users and potential shapers of future AI tools.

Equally if not more important to consider is the **environmental impact** of GenAI tools. The increasing demands to extract the rare minerals needed to produce the hardware to run AI at scale is but one element of an amplifying supply chain servicing the increasing use of AI (Crawford, 2021). The environmental costs of using GenAI tools to do similar tasks such as functioning as search engines is much higher, and the rapidly expanding real estate, power and water usage of giant data centres (that is, ‘the cloud’) are also much higher than even existing forms of big tech (Hogan, 2024; Kneese & Young, 2024). All the while, AI companies are selling a dream that AI tools will be instrumental in solving environmental crises (Zehner & Ullrich, 2024). For children and young people there is a very real threat that AI will exacerbate the many

environmental challenges they are already going to inherit despite the “computational promise” they represent, which is a “paradox” worth foregrounding (Hogan, 2024). Research will be needed to not just address *how* GenAI tools are used but also *when and if* their use is appropriate at all given the much higher comparative environmental costs.

Finally, the challenge which really flags the urgency for research on how AI impacts children’s lives is **the rapid integration and ubiquity of AI tools across the breadth of contemporary societies**. In a rush to justify the enormous investments made in creating ever larger LLMs, tech companies have developed AI tools for use in healthcare, employment services, in creative spaces and industries, and across the educational sectors to name just a small sample. Similarly, apps and platforms including Photoshop, Canva, Microsoft’s Office Suite, Instagram, Snapchat and many others have integrated their own GenAI tools and agents, mostly accessible with a single click. For children and young people, the question is not where they will come across AI, but rather where won’t they.

Looking Forward

The companies selling AI tools have cultivated an aura of alchemical exceptionalism since GenAI can produce such convincing novel outputs, be that human-like conversations, stories, essays, images, or even video and voices. These big tech companies are also selling their vision of the future, a future where human-like and superhuman level digital intelligences are just around the corner. However, the realities of glitching and inaccurate tools do not match the marketing hype, and worse, the hype obscures the very real costs that these technologies represent. The challenge for researchers and educators is to equip today’s children and young people to be critical and selective users of AI technologies, ensuring they have the critical digital and data literacies to know how AI systems work, and to judge when the cost of using these tools is justified, ethical and trustworthy. In a world where access to AI tools is ubiquitous, having the educational and literacy scaffolding to make the most of AI tools both in choosing when to use them, and when not to, is vital for young people. For researchers of children and media, AI amplifies the need for analyses of existing issues such as children’s data privacy, while also provoking a range of new questions including the way young people relate to and understand tools and agents which convincingly mimic humanlike interactions. As big tech companies force new AI tools into the everyday lives of children and young people, it is incumbent on researchers to force their way into these spaces as well.

Author Biographies

Tama Leaver (PhD) is a Professor of Internet Studies at Curtin University, a Chief Investigator in the ARC Centre of Excellence for the Digital Child, and the Immediate Past President of the Association of Internet Researchers (AoIR). His current research focuses on children’s data, datafication and impact of Generative AI tools. Tama’s online presence is www.tamaleaver.net.

Suzanne Srdarov (PhD) teaches in media and digital cultures, and has a particular interest in media cultures and their intersections with gender. She is a researcher in the ARC Centre of Excellence for the Digital Child.

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